

COMPUTER SIMULATION OF DEPOSITION OF LOW ATOMIC CLUSTERS ON THE SURFACE OF CRYSTALS

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Annotation. In this work, using computer simulation based on the method of molecular dynamics, the process of deposition of silver clusters (Ag_{20} and Ag_{60}) on the surface of a copper crystal is simulated. The EAM potential was used to calculate the processes of cluster interaction with atoms of the crystal surface. At the first stage of modeling, the equilibrium configuration of Ag_{20} and Ag_{60} metal clusters was found. At the second stage of modeling, a model of a 4000-atom copper crystal was constructed. At the third stage of modeling, Ag_{20} and Ag_{60} clusters with different energies were deposited vertically on the copper crystal surface.

Keywords: atom, cluster, silver, molecular dynamics, potential (EAM).

Intraduction. Clusters are very different from solid materials. They are nanosized aggregates with an intermediate state of matter between molecules and volume. They also have a number of unusual physical and chemical properties such as structural, electronic and thermodynamic. Metal clusters have been the subject of intense research. Due to their wide application in biology, catalysis, and nanotechnology, research on clusters has shown significant development in both experimental and theoretical studies. Understanding the complex relationship between atomic and electronic structure can be an important preliminary step towards the possible use of metal nanoclusters in future nanotechnology applications.

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Computer simulation techniques have become important in research because of their ability to "connect" theory and experiment. In addition, computer simulations can often be carried out under conditions close to experimental conditions, and the obtained simulation results can be directly compared with experimental observations. This, in turn, makes computer simulation a very powerful tool for understanding phenomena based on experimental observations, as well as for exploring areas that are unattainable by experiment [1,3].

Results and discussion. At the first stage of modeling, equilibrium configurations of metal clusters Ag₂₀ and Ag₆₀ were found. At the second stage of modeling, models of a copper crystal with the (001) orientation for the surface were constructed. At the third stage of modeling, silver clusters with different energies (1 eV/atom and 10 eV/atom) were deposited vertically on the surface of a copper crystal. As can be seen from Fig. 1, as a result of deposition, some of the atoms of the Ag₂₀ cluster are immersed in the target, and the clusters are significantly deformed. As the energy of the cluster increases, the depth of immersion to the surface increases. Figure 2 shows that the deposition of Ag₆₀ silver clusters on the surface of copper crystals, with an increase in the energy and size of the cluster, the depth of its penetration into the crystal increases.

Conclusion. The simulation results show that the penetration of clusters into the target depends both on their energy and on their sizes, with the size dependence being stronger. Information is given on the effects of cluster penetration into a crystal, its deformation, and lattice distortions, with emphasis on the size and stoichiometry of the cluster.

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